

Journal home page:
<http://www.iajpr.com/index.php/en/>

INDO AMERICAN
 JOURNAL OF
 PHARMACEUTICAL
 RESEARCH

Comparative study of UV Spectrophotometric methods for quantitative determination of Tiapride Hydrochloride in physical mixture by one way ANOVA technique

Panchal Vihang U.^{1*}, K.S.Muralikrishna¹, Chauhan Prakash S.¹, Dudhat Pradip R.¹, Mistry Dhaval H.², Desai Lay H.³, Shah Jemin R.⁴

¹Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College, Department of Quality assurance, Kim, Surat-394110 Gujarat, India.

²Gujarat Forensic Sciences University, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

³I S F College of Pharmacy, Moga, Punjab, India.

⁴Baroda College of Pharmacy, Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 28/12/2012
 Available online
 22/01/2013

Keywords

Tiapride Hydrochloride,
 Zero order
 Spectroscopy,
 Derivative
 Spectroscopy,
 Area under curve
 method,
 ANOVA.

ABSTRACT

A novel drug named Tiapride Hydrochloride is used in management of behavioral disorders and in treatment of dyskinesias. Four different simple, accurate, rapid, economical and reproducible spectroscopic methods namely Zero order, First derivative, Second derivative and Area Under Curve(AUC) spectroscopy have been developed and validated for estimation of Tiapride Hydrochloride in physical mixture using distilled water as a solvent according to ICH Guidelines Q2(R1). These methods obey Beer's law in the range of 20-70 µg/ml for Tiapride Hydrochloride. Absorbance of each solution was measured at 287.20 nm for zero order spectrophotometry. First derivative spectra are obtained by transformations at $\Delta\lambda$ of 4 nm and scaling factor 1 and absorbance measured at 301.40 nm. Second derivative spectra are obtained by transformations at $\Delta\lambda$ of 8 nm and scaling factor 10 and absorbance measured at 307 nm. Peak area is measured between 280.20-294.20 nm for AUC method. The methods showed good reproducibility and recovery with %RSD less than 1. All these four methods were compared statistically. Statistical comparisons by one way ANOVA shows all methods have equal applicability for estimation of Tiapride Hydrochloride in physical mixture. So, the proposed methods were found to be simple, specific, accurate, precise, linear and robust. Hence, all four methods can be equally applied for routine analysis of Tiapride Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical formulations.

Corresponding author

Panchal Vihang U, Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College, SET's campus, Near Railway Station, Kim (E), Surat, Gujarat, India, vihang8@yahoo.co.in *Contact No.: +919979884908

Please cite this article in press as Panchal V U et.al. Comparative study of UV Spectrophotometric methods for quantitative determination of Tiapride Hydrochloride in physical mixture by one way ANOVA technique. Indo American Journal of Pharm Research.2013;2(12).

Copy right © 2013 This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Indo American journal of Pharmaceutical Research, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

INTRODUCTION

Tiapride Hydrochloride is a selective dopamine D₂ receptor antagonist and mainly used in management of behavioral disorders and in treatment of dyskinesias. Chemically it is N-[2-(Diethylamino)ethyl]-2-methoxy-5-(methylsulphonyl) benzamide hydrochloride¹. It is a substituted benzamide that exhibits anti-psychotic properties. Ph.Eur., USP, BP are official handbooks (pharmacopoeias) in which methods of analysis with specifications for substances are laid down by the authorities of the EU, USA, or UK respectively². Literature survey revealed that several methods have been reported for the estimation of Tiapride Hydrochloride. These include HPLC³⁻⁶, GC^{7,8}, HPTLC⁹, Ion selective electrodes¹⁰, Voltammetry¹¹, Capillary electrophoresis¹² and Flow injection chemiluminometry¹³. So, we decided to work towards development and validation of simple, sensitive, accurate, precise, rugged and economic spectroscopic method for determination of the drug in physical mixture. The present work describes a four validated UV spectroscopic methods for determination of the drug in physical mixture.

Chemical Structure of Tiapride Hydrochloride

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentation:

- A double-beam UV-Visible spectrophotometer, model Shimadzu UV-2450 having two matched cells with 1-cm light path
- Semi micro analytical balance (Sartorius CD2250, Germany)
- Sonicator (Trans-O-sonic)
- Volumetric flasks – 10ml, 50ml, 100ml
- Pipettes – 1ml, 5ml, 10ml, beakers, measuring cylinders.

Chemicals and Reagents:

- Authentic sample of Tiapride Hydrochloride purchased from Sigma Aldrich, India
- Distilled water

Experimental condition:

According to the solubility characteristics, the suitable solvent for the drug was found to be distilled water.

Preparation of standard stock solution: Accurately weighed Tiapride Hydrochloride (10 mg) was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask. 50 ml distilled water was added to the flask. The drug was dissolved and the final volume was adjusted with distilled water up to the mark to prepare a 100 µg/ml stock solution of drug.

Method-A: Zero Order UV Spectroscopic Method

To determine wavelength for measurement, six working standard solutions having different concentrations in the range of 20-70 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Tiapride Hydrochloride were scanned between 200-400 nm against distilled water. The drug showed maximum absorbance at 287.20 nm, which was used for the further validation. Beer's law is obeyed in this concentration range.

Method-B: First Derivative Spectroscopic Method

A derivative spectroscopy shows the rate of change over a specified wavelength range and can produce hidden peaks. All zero order spectra were transformed in derivative command by transformation function of UV Probe software (version 2.33). Delta lambda ($\Delta\lambda$) increase smoothing and scaling factor(SF) increase multiplication of raw spectra. Tiapride Hydrochloride shows broad peak in zero order spectra so to minimize baseline interference first order spectra were optimized for better result by using function $\Delta\lambda$ and scaling factor. Optimum results were obtained in the measuring wavelength range 270-310 nm (SF=1, $\Delta\lambda = 4$ nm) for first derivative spectrophotometric method. First order derivative curves showed one maximum and one minimum and statistical comparison shows 0.9997 regression coefficient at 301.40 nm. So, 301.40 nm was selected for further study.

Method-C: Second Derivative Spectroscopic Method

The second derivative spectra were computed from the zero order absorption spectra using UV Probe 2.33 software. These transformations were carried out at $\Delta\lambda=8$ and scaling factor 10. Amplitudes of second derivative spectra were recorded at 280-310 nm. Second order derivative curves showed one maximum and two minimum and statistical comparison shows 0.9995 regression coefficient at 307 nm. So, 307 nm was selected for further study.

Method-D: Area Under Curve Spectroscopic Method

Peak area were optimized in zero order spectra for area under curve measurement and peak area between 280.20 and 294.20 nm for Tiapride Hydrochloride shows 0.9991 regression coefficient, therefore this wavelength range was selected for further study.

Validation of the proposed methods:

The proposed methods were validated according to International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines¹⁴.

Figure 1.1: Calibration curve of Tiapride Hydrochloride by Zero order spectroscopy method

Figure 1.2: Zero order spectra of Tiapride Hydrochloride

Figure 2.1: Calibration curve of Tiapride Hydrochloride by First order derivative spectroscopy

Figure 2.2: First derivative spectra of Tiapride Hydrochloride

Figure 3.1: Calibration curve of Tiapride Hydrochloride by Second order derivative spectroscopy

Figure 3.2: Second derivative spectra of Tiapride Hydrochloride

Figure 4.1: Calibration curve of Tiapride Hydrochloride by Area under curve spectroscopic method

Linearity: Linearity was checked from the spectra of six different concentrations of the drug. Tiapride Hydrochloride showed linearity in the concentration range of 20-70 µg/ml and calibration curves [n=6] were plotted between absorbance and concentration of drugs.

Precision: The precision of the method was confirmed by repeatability and intermediate precision. The repeatability was performed by the analysis of the drug and it was repeated for three times with the same concentration. The intermediate precision of the method was confirmed by intraday and interday analysis i.e. the analysis of the drug for 3 different concentrations (30, 50, 70 µg/ml) was repeated three times in the same day and on three successive days. The result was reported in terms of relative standard deviation (% RSD).

Sensitivity: The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) parameters were calculated, in accordance with ICH guidelines, $LOD=3.3\sigma/S$ and $LOQ=10\sigma/S$ respectively, where σ is the standard deviation of the response and S is the slope of the calibration curve.

Accuracy: To check the accuracy of the developed method, analytical recovery experiments were carried out by using standard addition method in three different concentrations. Known amounts of standard solution of Tiapride Hydrochloride were added at 80, 100 and 120% level to prequantified sample solution of physical mixture (20 µg/ml). The amount of Tiapride Hydrochloride was estimated by applying obtained values to the respective regression line equations. From the total amount of drug found, the percentage recovery was calculated. This procedure was repeated for three times for each concentration.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Linearity:

The responses of Tiapride Hydrochloride were linear in the concentration range of 20-70 µg/ml with coefficient of correlation $r^2 = 0.9998$ for zero order UV spectroscopic method. The responses for other three methods were also linear in the same concentration range. The results are shown in Table 1 and Figures 1 to 4.

Precision:

Precision was calculated as intra and inter day variation (%RSD) for the drug. The results are shown in Table 3.

Accuracy:

Accuracy was determined by calculating the recovery and the mean was determined. The results are shown in Table 3.

Analysis of Physical Mixture:

Physical mixture was prepared by mixing Tiapride Hydrochloride with the excipients in proper proportions. This mixture was optimized by IR spectroscopy and DSC technique. No interference due to excipients was observed. The assay results are described in Table 2. It may therefore be inferred that degradation of Tiapride Hydrochloride had not occurred in the physical mixture that was analyzed by these methods.

Statistical comparison of the results obtained by the developed methods by one way ANOVA:

To compare the differences among the methods, an ANOVA test was applied to four different spectroscopic methods: Zero order UV spectroscopy, First derivative spectroscopy, Second derivative spectroscopy and Area under curve spectroscopic method. Assay results in form of 3 replicates from each method were taken in account for performing the ANOVA test. Results of Statistical comparisons are shown in Table 4.

Table 1: Linearity study data of Tiapride Hydrochloride.

Sr. No.	Conc. ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Zero order UV Spectroscopic Method	First derivative Spectroscopic method	Second derivative Spectroscopic method	Area Under Curve Spectroscopic Method
		287.20 nm	301.40 nm ($\Delta\lambda=4$, SF [#] 1)	307 nm ($\Delta\lambda=8$, SF [#] 10)	280.20-294.20 nm
		Absorb.* \pm CV	$\partial A/\partial\lambda^*$ \pm %CV	$\partial^2 A/\partial\lambda^2$* \pm CV	Area* \pm %CV
1.	20	0.2209 \pm 0.0414	0.0151 \pm 0.0292	0.0146 \pm 0.0334	0.2367 \pm 0.0409
2.	30	0.3223 \pm 0.0416	0.0228 \pm 0.0435	0.0221 \pm 0.0426	0.3495 \pm 0.0493
3.	40	0.4349 \pm 0.0391	0.0306 \pm 0.0375	0.0297 \pm 0.0408	0.4815 \pm 0.0490
4.	50	0.5456 \pm 0.0426	0.0382 \pm 0.0402	0.0371 \pm 0.0382	0.5966 \pm 0.0225
5.	60	0.6474 \pm 0.0361	0.0453 \pm 0.0350	0.0436 \pm 0.0323	0.7048 \pm 0.0376
6.	70	0.7617 \pm 0.0353	0.0537 \pm 0.0369	0.0512 \pm 0.0320	0.8421 \pm 0.0317

*Mean of six determinations, #scaling factor

Table 2: Assay study of Tiapride Hydrochloride.

Physical mixture	Zero order UV Spectroscopic method	First derivative Spectroscopic method	Second derivative Spectroscopic method	Area under curve Spectroscopic method
	% Assay \pm SD	% Assay \pm SD	% Assay \pm SD	% Assay \pm SD
100 mg	99.8457 \pm 0.1626	99.5833 \pm 0.3608	99.3571 \pm 0.1237	99.2361 \pm 0.2097

CONCLUSION

From the results obtained by applying the suggested procedure, it is obvious that the proposed methods were accurate, precise, simple, sensitive, selective, and rapid. From the results of statistical comparison, the calculated F value did not exceed the theoretical F value, at 0.05 level of significance, thus proposed methods give reproducible results and can be applied successfully in routine analysis for the estimation of Tiapride Hydrochloride.

Table 3: Summary of validation parameters of Tiapride Hydrochloride.

Sr. No	Parameters	Zero order UV Spectroscopic method	First derivative Spectroscopic method	Second derivative Spectroscopic method	Area under curve Spectroscopic method
1	λ max (nm)	287.20	301.40	307	280.20-294.20
2	Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	20-70	20-70	20-70	20-70
3	Regression equation	$y = 0.0108x + 0.0015$	$y = 0.0008x - 0.0002$	$y = 0.0007x + 0.0002$	$y = 0.0120x - 0.0058$
4	Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9998	0.9997	0.9995	0.9991
5	Precision				
	Intraday (n = 9) (% RSD)	0.22-0.52	0.51-0.79	0.61-0.82	0.48-0.96
	Interday (n = 9) (% RSD)	0.54-0.68	0.24-0.94	0.44-0.86	0.34-0.83
6	Accuracy (% Recovery)	99.17-99.67	99.27-99.76	99.34-99.52	99.31-99.79
7	LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.3331	1.6041	2.5123	2.0591
8	LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	7.0699	4.8609	7.6131	6.2397
9	Assay (%)	99.85	99.58	99.36	99.24

Table 4: Result of one way ANOVA of spectroscopic methods.

Source of Variation	Df	Sum of Squares	Mean of Squares	F calculated
Between groups	3	0.6491	0.2164	
Within groups	8	0.4319	0.0540	4.0079
Total	11	1.0810		

*F theoretical = 4.0662 at P = 0.05

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are highly thankful to Shree Dhanvantary Pharmacy College, Kim, Surat, Gujarat, India for providing all facilities to carry out the work. We are also thankful to Sigma Aldrich, India for helping us purchasing the drug sample for successfully undergoing this work.

REFERENCES

1. British Pharmacopoeia Vol.II. The Department of Health. London: The Stationery Office; 2009.
2. Public Assessment Report of the Medicines Evaluation Board in the Netherlands. MEB pursuant Article 21 (3) and (4) of Directive 2001/83/EC.
3. Li J, Shao Y-h, Cui X-d. Determination of Tiapride Hydrochloride Injection and related substances by HPLC. Qilu Pharmaceutical Affairs 2005;(6).
4. Nobilis M, Vybiralova Z, Szotakova B, Sladkova K, Kunes M, Svoboda Z. High-performance liquid chromatographic determination of Tiapride and its phase I metabolite in blood plasma using tandem UV photodiode-array and fluorescence detection. Journal of Chromatography B 2011;879(32):3845-52.
5. Chiba R, Ogasawara A, Kubo T, Yamazaki H, Umino M, Ishizuka Y. Direct determination of benzamides in serum by column-switching high-performance liquid chromatography. Analytical Sciences 2003;19:785-9.
6. Duan G, Lu M, Wu B. Reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic determination of Tiapride in plasma and urine. Yao Xue Xue Bao 1986;21(12):917-21.
7. Ishii A, Kumazawa T, Seno H, Nishikawa M, Watanabe K, Suzuki O. Sensitive detection of benzamides by gas chromatography with surface ionization detection and their rapid clean-up from body fluids. Japanese Journal of Forensic Toxicology 1995;13(3):216-22.
8. Kamizono A, Inotsume N, Miyamoto L, Ueda K, Miyakawa T, Arimoto H, et al. Determination of Sultopride and Tiapride in serum by gas chromatography using a surface ionisation detector. Journal of Chromatography 1991;567(1):113-20.
9. Katarina R, Slavica F, Katarina N, Danica A. TLC determination of Tiapride Hydrochloride and its impurities in pharmaceuticals. Journal of Liquid Chromatography and Related Technologies 2012;35(10):1336-45.
10. Metwally FH. Membrane sensors for the selective determination of Tiapride in presence of its degradation products. Yakugaku Zasshi 2007;127(8):1267-73.
11. Zayed SIM. Differential pulse anodic voltammetric determination of Tiapride Hydrochloride in pharmaceutical preparation and human urine using carbon paste electrodes. Analytical Sciences 2011;27(5):535-9.
12. Li J, Zhao F, Ju H. Simultaneous electrochemiluminescence determination of Sulpiride and Tiapride by capillary electrophoresis with cyclodextrin additives. Journal of Chromatography B 2006;835:84-9.
13. Aly FA, Alarfaj NA, A. A, Alwarthan. Flow-injection chemiluminometric analysis of some benzamides by their sensitizing effect on the cerium-sulphite reaction. Talanta 2001;54:715-25.
14. ICH guideline Q2 (R1). Validation of analytical procedures: text and methodology. Geneva: 1996.

Submit your next manuscript to *IAJPR* and take advantage of:

- Access Online first
- Double blind peer review policy
- No space constraints
- Rapid publication
- International recognition

Submit your manuscript at: editorinchief@iajpr.com